

An Assessment of Knowledge of Rape Among Women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria

Author(s), KURE, Laraba (RM, RN, CHO, B.Sc, RME, BNSc.)

AND

Dr. OWOPETU, Christiana Adetoun (RN, RM, PhD)

Abstract:

This study investigated the knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro community of Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. The study used experimental design as its guide. The population of the study constituted of the 4000 women in the community who were between the ages of 15 and 49 years old. A sample of 120 participants was selected using convenient sampling technique. A self-structured designed questionnaire titled Women Knowledge of Rape Questionnaire (WOKR-Q) based on the 4-point rating scale was used. The face to face administration was used to collect the data. The questionnaire was validated by experts, while its reliability was determined using the Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded coefficient value of 0.89. Frequency table, mean scores, standard deviation and independent t-test were employed as methods of data analysis. The study used decision rule of 2.5 – 4.0 as good knowledge and 0 – 2.4 as poor knowledge for answering the research questions. The hypothesis was tested using t-test at significance level of 0.05. The findings revealed that the participants agreed that rape is a crime against humanity, but it has no definite definition in Nigeria. It was also found that mouth penetration of another person with penis without his or her consent is rape and anal penetration of another person with penis without his consent

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constitutes rape. The results showed that there was a significant difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean scores of women knowledge of rape in the study Area. The study concluded that women had good knowledge of rape in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State and recommended among others that women should be constantly trained on what constitutes rape so as to increase their knowledge of rape as a way of curbing rape cases in communities.

Keywords: Assessment, Rape, Knowledge of Rape, Women,

About Author

Author(s):

KURE, Laraba (RM, RN, CHO, B.Sc, RME, BNSc.)
Department of Maternal and Child Health Nursing,
School of Nursing Science,
Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria.

And

Dr. OWOPETU, Christiana Adetoun (RN, RM, PhD)
Department of Nursing Science,
Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Rape is one of the several forms of violence against women. It is an infringement on women's privacy, self-preservation, rights and dignity. Print and electronic media evidences revealed that rape issue is now a serious social challenge; it is a criminal act that affects a lot of women in the society. Rape cases in Nigeria have been associated with factors that cut across poverty, family, care givers, institutions, and legal issues. Tade and Udechukwu (2020) submitted that rape has become a usual trend in Nigeria that female ladies and minor alike are raped and murdered, infants as young as 3 months and children below 10 years are raped by men old enough to be their grandfathers, teachers rape students, housemates are raped by their masters, fathers rape their daughters, traditional rulers rape their subjects, religious leaders rape their members, a boss has raped his staff, a minor raped a minor, robbers raping mothers, daughters,. Suprakash, et al., (2017) posited that sexual assault survivors undergo numerous psychological problems such as, anxiety disorders, Post Traumatic Stress disorders, and depression, deliberate self-harm and sleep disorders.

The scourge of rape is not a new societal problem in both low and high-income countries, but the general agreement is that the understanding and extent to which rape cases are handled at both family and national levels are different. In most developing countries in particular, the rate at which rape victims die has become usual headlines on the mass and social media recently. Chiazor, et al (2016) reported that there are about 147,000 rape cases in UK yearly and very few are convicted. The National Bureau of Statistics (2018) reported that the annual highest rape occurrence in Nigeria was recorded for ages 13 years and above over 3 years of 2014, 2015 and 2016 and was given as 175, 200, 255 respectively. The report also stated that the national rape incidence for women and girls from 2015 -2017, in Nigeria was 63.0%, 72.1% and 69.3% respectively. The rape incidence at home was 67.5%, 76.7% and 69.3% respectively as show by the data while the rape incidence in school was 53.8 and 56.9% in 2015 and 2016 but increased to 93.4 in 2017.

A report by UNICEF (2021) showed that before the age of 18, 1 in 4 Nigerian girls are sexually assaulted. This suggests that rape can occur at religious worship centre, malls, home, school or other places. In the light of these heart-breaking revelations, Alao (2018) contended that rape in the society is actually a crime to the victims, the society and the nations' economic and social development at large. These statistics therefore elucidate that rape is worldwide issue as such, Plateau State and Jos North in particular where the seat of government is and the commercial nerve centre of the State cannot be immune of the challenge of Rape owing to its cosmopolitan nature. Consequently, Davou, et al, (2017) discovered rape prevalence in Jos North was 31.0% (28.2% in females and 2.8% among males in their study. The scholars however failed to concentrate on the situation in Jenta Mangoro community.

There seems to be feminism in the debate on rape cases in Nigeria because the proportion of women to men that have been raped in various parts of the nation tend to show that female victims are more than the male victims. Peters and Olowa (2010) cited in Chiedu (2013) and reported that in Lagos state, western Nigeria, there were about 10,079 cases, which is 18% incidence between 2001 and 2005. In an effort to tame this scourge in Nigeria, many steps were taken by both Non-governmental Organization and the government.

Furthermore, Plateau State government has also domesticated the child right law that contains sections that deals with rape cases, the Federal of Women Lawyers also have been involved in educating women on the rights and on issues related to rape. Despite these efforts, realities on ground show that rape cases are still among the greatest social problem facing developing countries like Nigeria. The Child Rights Law in Nigeria 31(2) enacted by the federal government in May 2003, anyone convicted for rape is liable to life imprisonment. Odeh (2013), Ashiru and Orifowomo (2015) and Gbadamosi (2021) observed that the law is not been enforced creating a situation where females are being raped in most communities. This suggest that if this problem is left to continue, the incidence of rape in communities like Jenta Mangoro where social vices such as drug and substance abuse, youth restiveness and cultism seems to be on the increase will keep increasing.

Amidst this challenge, most studies on rape seem to have concentrated more on the causes and prevention of rape generally. There is paucity of literature on the knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North in particular. Furthermore, studies on rape also employed mostly descriptive survey design whose main aim is to generalize on the study population. This research on the other hand used experimental design as its guide on the belief that similar studies could be replicated. Chiazor, et al., (2016) rightly observed that knowledge of the implications of rape may be a factor that can deter the intended sexual offenders and re-offenders to halting the crime of rape. Thus, it could be that the extents of knowledge of rape among women who are mostly vulnerable to rape make them prone to being raped in the community. This is the main motivation for the present research. Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess the level of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the pre-intervention mean score of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area;
2. evaluate the difference between pre-intervention and post-intervention mean score of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. What is the pre-intervention mean score of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area?
2. What is the extent of difference between pre-intervention and post-intervention mean score of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area?

Research Hypothesis

A null hypothesis was developed that guide the study;

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean score of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area.

Methodology

The researcher used Quasi-experimental design for the study. The researcher used one-group pre-test post-test design that provides a comparison between a group of subjects before and after the experimental treatment. A training package of what constitutes rape was designed by the researcher. The study population of this study was 4000 women who are residents of Jenta Mangoro Community in Jos North. The study however used a sample size of 120 women who were selected from the different settlements that made up Jenta Mangoro community. This number consisted of singles, married women, separated and those that have been divorced and were all Christians between the ages of 15 to 49 years. The researcher used convenient sampling for the study. A convenience sampling technique is a method where the units that are selected for inclusion in the sample are the easiest to access.

This study used a self-designed structured questionnaire titled 'Women Knowledge of Rape Questionnaire (WOKR-Q)' was developed by the researcher considering the women's level of knowledge on rape and on prevention of rape. The instrument was validated by experts in Nursing Science who ensured the face and content validity. The reliability of the instrument was ensured through the internal consistency method. It involved 20 participants while the data collected were subjected to Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded coefficient value of 0.89. This value was higher than 0.70 used as the reliability benchmark, which implies that the instrument was statistically reliable. The data was compiled, coded and prepared for analysis. Basically, descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the pre-intervention mean score of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area?

Table 1: Results of Pre-Intervention Mean Score of Women Knowledge of Rape

SN	Statement of Items	N	Mean \bar{X}	Std. Deviation
1	Rape is a crime against humanity	120	3.681	0.733
2	Rape has no definite definition in Nigeria	120	3.678	0.818
3	Rape is when a man has sex with a woman by force	120	3.176	0.898
4	Mouth penetration of another person with penis without his/her consent is rape	120	3.611	0.616
5	Rape is said to occur when a man has vaginal sex without a woman's consent	120	3.427	0.884
6	Rape is unwanted, forcible sex with a man against the woman's will	120	3.362	0.799
7	Anal penetration of another person with penis without his consent is also known as rape	120	3.173	0.838
8	Rape is a man pretending to be a woman's husband and having sex with her	120	3.489	0.699

9	Rape is when a man degrades, humiliates and inflicts pain on a woman during sex	120	3.438	0.742
10	Putting one's finger into another's vagina without consent is rape	120	3.005	0.922

Cumulative Mean = 3.404

Criterion = 2.5

The findings from the analysis of women knowledge of rape in Table 2 showed that respondents agreed that rape is a crime against humanity ($\bar{X}=3.681$), rape has no definite definition in Nigeria ($\bar{X}=3.678$), mouth penetration of another person with penis without his/her consent is rape ($\bar{X}=3.611$), anal penetration of another person with penis without his consent is also known as rape ($\bar{X}=3.173$) and putting one's finger into another's vagina without consent is rape ($\bar{X}=3.005$) respectively. However, since the cumulative mean score of 3.404 for all the items falls within 2.5-4.0 decision rule for good knowledge, this implies that women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North had good knowledge of rape.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of difference between pre-intervention and post-intervention mean score of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area?

Table 2: Summary of Pre-Intervention and Post-Intervention Mean Scores of Women Knowledge of Rape

Knowledge of Rape	Mean \bar{X}	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Pre-Intervention	3.404	1.161	0.233
Post-Intervention	3.637	0.073	

The findings from the results of independent t-test analysis of the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean scores of women's knowledge of rape in Table 2 revealed a pre-intervention mean score of 3.404 and a post-intervention mean score of 3.637 respectively. The standard deviations revealed that the deviations of the individual scores from the mean for the post-intervention were closer compared to that of the pre-intervention scores. The results further showed a mean score difference of 0.233 which indicated that there was an improvement of 23.3% in the mean scores of the participants after exposure to the treatment or due to the post-intervention. Furthermore, since the post-intervention mean score of 3.637 falls between the decision rule of 2.5 to 4.0, it implies that the women had good knowledge of rape in the community.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean score of knowledge of rape among women in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area.

Table 4: Summary of Independent t-Test Results of Differences between Pre-Intervention and Post-intervention Mean Scores of Women Knowledge of Rape

Knowledge of Rape	\bar{X}	SD	Df.	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Pre-Intervention	3.404	1.161	368	4.681	.000	Sig.
Post-Intervention	3.637	0.073				

$p < 0.05$

The findings from the analysis of the difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean scores of women knowledge of rape in Table 3 revealed that $t(368)=4.681, p=.000$; hence $p < 0.05$. Based on this finding, there was no enough evidence to accept the null hypothesis. The study rejected the null hypothesis and the conclusion drawn is that there is a significant difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean scores of women knowledge of rape in Jenta Mangoro community of Jos North in Plateau State, Nigeria.

Discussion

The results of analysis of women knowledge of rape revealed that is a crime against humanity, rape has no definite definition in Nigeria, mouth penetration of another person with penis without his/her consent is rape, anal penetration of another person with penis without his consent is also known as rape and putting one's finger into another's vagina without consent is rape. This supports the view of Chiazor et al., (2016) and Chukwuka and Kitause (2014) that rape is the act of forcefully having sex with someone against their will. Imosemi and Adedamola (2018) also had argued that rape is defined as one of the most pervasive forms of violence against women and a crime in which the assailant uses sex to inflict humiliation on the victim or exerts power and control over the victim. Furthermore, the findings also revealed that the cumulative mean scores of the items indicated that women in Jenta Mangoro had good knowledge of rape. The findings on knowledge of rape however contradicted the findings of Aborisade (2016) who found that finger penetration (fingering) and penetration of the mouth by penis are not real sex.

Similarly, the findings from the analysis of the difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean scores of women's knowledge of rape revealed a pre-intervention mean score of 3.141 and a post-intervention mean score of 3.537 respectively. Therefore, since the post-intervention mean score of 3.537 falls between the decision rules of 2.5 to 4.0, it implies that the women had good knowledge of rape in the community. Furthermore, the findings revealed that the mean difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean scores of women knowledge of rape in the Area was 0.396. The implication of this is that there was an increase of 39.6% in the mean scores of the participants after been exposure to the treatment being a lecture on rape. The results of this analysis also means that women knowledge of rape can be enhance by giving them lectures on what constitute rape cases in their communities. Aborisade (2016) and Ogunbode et al (2014) stated that higher institutions in the country should establish anti-sexual assault units within the campuses to educate and counsel students about sexual victimization and safe sex, while young woman should be enlightened about the health implication of nonconsensual sex, irrespective of their emotional attachment to the offender. This could be organized with

specialized women's right organizations that could provide capacity building support and logistics services.

Similarly, Imosemi and Adedamola (2018) asserted that there should be public sensitization and awareness so that the society will know the victims are not to blame and they can give adequate support to them. More so, the finding from the hypothesis revealed that $p < 0.05$, which indicated that there is a significant difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean scores of women knowledge of rape in Jenta Mangoro community of Jos North of Plateau State, Nigeria. The results of this analysis contradicted the study of Ibekwe et al (2018) who found that 50.0% of the participants had poor knowledge of rape but that knowledge of rape increased significantly by level of study

Conclusion

The findings from the results of analysis revealed that rape is a crime against humanity, but it has no definite definition in Nigeria. However, acts such as mouth penetration of another person with penis without his or her consent are rape and anal penetration of another person with penis without his consent constitutes rape. The results showed that there was a significant difference between the pre-intervention and post-intervention mean scores of women knowledge of rape in the study Area. The study therefore concluded that women had good knowledge of rape in Jenta Mangoro Community of Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this empirical study and the conclusion drawn, the following have been recommended among others:

- i. Women should be constantly trained on what constitutes rape so as to increase their knowledge of rape as a way of curbing rape cases in communities
- ii. Parents and community leaders should be involve in enlightening young girls on morals and dangers of indecent dressing an acts that could lead to rape
- iii. Government should ensure that perpetrators of rape cases are prosecuted so as to serve as deterrent to others who may want to practice the act in communities.

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